

Application of Analysis Methods for Vaccine Efficacy in a Dengue Trial

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BACKGROUND

The vaccine efficacy (VE) is defined as the reduction of relative risk of disease: $VE=1-(R_v/R_p)$, where R_v and R_p are the incidence rates of the disease of interest in the vaccine and placebo groups, respectively. A conditional exact method proposed by Chan and Bohidar [1] is often used to estimate the vaccine efficacy and its confidence interval. In this poster, as previously considered in [11], we compare the conditional exact method with two alternative approaches: Poisson regression and modified Poisson regression proposed by Zou [6] by using trial data, with and without follow-up time adjustment.

KEY WORDS

Vaccine efficacy, conditional exact method, Poisson regression, modified Poisson regression

INTRODUCTION

Currently, dengue is endemic in more than 100 countries in Africa, the Americas, the Eastern Mediterranean, South-East Asia, and the Western Pacific regions, and the circulation of multiple serotypes is common in the most affected countries [2]. It is estimated that there might be 390 million people suffering from dengue infections every year of which 96 million have clinical manifestation [7]. The WHO estimates that approximately 3.9 billion people throughout the world live with the risk of contracting dengue. In addition, around 120 million people visit endemic regions every year [8]. In 2013 alone, 2.35 million cases of dengue were recorded in the Americas, of which 38,000 were of severe dengue [9].

The first documented epidemic of dengue fever in Brazil occurred between 1981 and 1982 in the city of Boa Vista, capital of the then Federal Territory of Roraima, when the dengue virus serotype 1 (DENV-1) and DENV-4 were isolated. The relative isolation of Roraima at the time helped to prevent the spread of the disease to other regions of Brazil [9].

Annual distribution of dengue cases/dengue serotypes are described in Figures 1 and 2. In 2015, 224,101 cases of dengue were notified in Brazil by Epidemiological Week 9, the beginning of the month of March. The southeast region had the highest number of notified cases (145,020 cases; 64.7%) in relation to the country total, followed by the central-west (34,125 cases; 15.2%), northeast (21,472 cases; 9.6%), north (12,001 cases; 5.4%) and south (11,483 cases; 5.1%). In 2015, an increase in the incidence (cases per 100,000 inhabitants) of dengue has been noted in every region of the country, with the greatest number being in the center-west and the southeast: 224.2 cases per 100,000 inhabitants and 170.4 cases per 100,000 inhabitants, respectively.

Figure 1. Annual Distribution of the Incidence of Reported Cases of Dengue (per 100,000 inhabitants), Brazil, 2008-2013. The median incidence during this period was 337 cases per 100,000 inhabitants.

Source: MS/SVS – National Disease Notification System (SINAN).

Figure 2. Distribution of Dengue Serotypes, Brazil, 2006-2014

Source: MS/SVS – National Disease Notification System (SINAN).

In an ongoing phase 3, double-blind trial in Brazil [10], with projected five years follow-up, a total of 16,235 participants were randomized 2:1, stratified by age (2-6, 7-17, and 18-59 years old), to receive Butantan-Dengue Vaccine or placebo. Primary objectives were to evaluate VE against symptomatic virologically confirmed dengue (VCD) by RT-PCR after Day 28 postvaccination to any serotype, regardless of dengue baseline serostatus and to describe safety up to Day 21. VE was assessed based upon 2-year follow up for each participant with 135 dengue cases. A total of 356 dengue cases were reported through the data cut-off of 13-JUL-2021 and their temporo-spatial distribution is described in the animation accessible through the following QR code:

METHODS

Using the data reported in [10], the primary efficacy analysis was performed on the per protocol (PP) population which includes all eligible and randomized participants who received the product to which they were allocated in accordance with the handling and administration conditions recommended by the manufacturer and did not use restricted medications, as per protocol. VE was calculated using the conditional exact method described by Chan & Bohidar [1]. The primary objective was considered met if the lower bound of the 2-sided 95% confidence interval (CI) of VE against symptomatic VCD caused by any dengue virus serotype was greater than 25%. In this poster, we compare three different methods of VE estimation.

Conditional Exact Method

When sample size is sufficiently large and the even rate is sufficiently small, a (number of cases in vaccine arm) and c (number of cases in placebo arm) approximately follow a Poisson distribution independently. Conditional on T , $a \sim \text{Binomial}(T, \theta)$, where $\theta = \frac{1-VE}{1+s-VE}$, s is the ratio of sample size (or follow-up times when adjusting for follow-up time) in the control to the vaccine group, and $T = a + c$ is the total number of cases. The estimate of VE is

$$\widehat{VE}_{exact} = \frac{(1+s) \times \hat{\theta} - 1}{\hat{\theta} - 1}$$

and the 95% CI of VE can be obtained from e.g., Clopper-Pearson or Blaker's method for the binomial parameter θ .

Poisson Regression

When Poisson regression is applied to binomial data, the logarithm link function can be used to model the risk R :

$$\log(R) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TRT \quad (\text{without adjusting for follow-up time})$$

or

$$\log(R) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TRT + \log(\text{follow-up time}), \quad (\text{adjusting for follow-up time})$$

where TRT is the treatment group (0 = placebo, 1 = vaccine).

The estimate of VE and its variance are

$$\widehat{VE}_p = 1 - \exp(\widehat{\beta}_1) = 1 - \frac{a(c+d)}{c(a+b)}, \quad \widehat{var}(\widehat{VE}_p) = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{c},$$

where b (resp., d) is the number of non-cases in vaccine (resp., placebo) arm.

Modified Poisson Regression

Zou [6] proposed a modified Poisson regression to handle overestimation of variance of \widehat{VE} in Poisson regression by using a robust error variance estimation known as sandwich estimation. The estimate of VE and its variance are

$$\widehat{VE}_{mp} = \widehat{VE}_p, \widehat{var}(\widehat{VE}_{mp}) = \frac{1}{a} - \frac{1}{a+b} + \frac{1}{c} - \frac{1}{c+d}.$$

RESULTS

Overall, 16,235 participants underwent randomization and received vaccine. The per protocol efficacy population included 16,162 participants. Per study design, approximately one third of participants were enrolled in each of the three age groups (2-6, 7-17, and 18-59 years old) (Table 1 [10]).

Table 1. Characteristics of the Participants at Baseline.*

	Vaccine (N = 10,259)	Placebo (N = 5976)	Total (N = 16,235)
Sex — no. (%)			
Female	5555 (54.1)	3216 (53.8)	8771 (54.0)
Male	4704 (45.9)	2760 (46.2)	7464 (46.0)
Age distribution — no. (%)			
2–6 yr	3337 (32.5)	1679 (28.1)	5016 (30.9)
7–17 yr	3376 (32.9)	1771 (29.6)	5147 (31.7)
18–59 yr	3546 (34.6)	2526 (42.3)	6072 (37.4)
Median age (IQR) — yr	11 (5–31)	14 (6–36)	12 (6–33)
Race or ethnic group — no. (%)†			
Pardo	7017 (68.4)	4036 (67.5)	11,053 (68.1)
White	2410 (23.5)	1402 (23.5)	3812 (23.5)
Black	655 (6.4)	408 (6.8)	1063 (6.5)
Asian	149 (1.5)	114 (1.9)	263 (1.6)
Indigenous or other	28 (0.3)	16 (0.3)	44 (0.3)
Hispanic ethnic group — no. (%)†			
No	10,068 (98.1)	5861 (98.1)	15,929 (98.1)
Yes	191 (1.9)	115 (1.9)	306 (1.9)
Previous exposure to DENV — no. (%)‡			
Yes			
Any serotype	5009 (48.8)	3041 (50.9)	8050 (49.6)
Monovalent	591 (5.8)	304 (5.1)	895 (5.5)
Bivalent	340 (3.3)	173 (2.9)	513 (3.2)
Trivalent	462 (4.5)	318 (5.3)	780 (4.8)
Tetravalent	3616 (35.2)	2246 (37.6)	5862 (36.1)
No	4855 (47.3)	2700 (45.2)	7555 (46.5)
Unknown or missing data§	395 (3.9)	235 (3.9)	630 (3.9)
Previous exposure to DENV, by serotype — no. (%)‡			
DENV-1	4295 (41.9)	2666 (44.6)	6961 (42.9)
DENV-2	4487 (43.7)	2766 (46.3)	7253 (44.7)
DENV-3	3801 (37.1)	2365 (39.6)	6166 (38.0)
DENV-4	4538 (44.2)	2791 (46.7)	7329 (45.1)
Unknown or missing data§	395 (3.9)	235 (3.9)	630 (3.9)

* Each participant can be counted in one or more applicable rows. DENV denotes dengue virus and VRNT₆₀ 60% virus reduction neutralization test.

† Race and ethnic group were reported by the participants. American Indian and Alaska Native were reported as Indigenous, Black and African American were reported as Black, multiracial Brazilian was reported as Pardo, and Hispanic and Latino were reported as Hispanic.

‡ Previous exposure to dengue virus is defined as a baseline DENV-1 VRNT₆₀ titer of at least 18, DENV-2 VRNT₆₀ titer of at least 15, DENV-3 VRNT₆₀ titer of at least 12, or DENV-4 VRNT₆₀ titer of at least 13.

§ Unknown results include missing test results and results from samples obtained from participants who did not provide written informed consent or who were not tested for DENV-3. Missing data denotes participants who did not undergo serologic testing because they did not provide informed consent or for other reasons.

Over the first two years of follow-up, vaccine efficacy (VE) against VCD of any DENV serotype was 79.6% (95% CI:70.0%-86.3%) (Table 2). Secondary endpoints of serotype-specific VE were 89.5% (95% CI:78.7%-95.0%) against DENV-1 and 69.6% (95% CI:50.8%-81.5%) against DENV-2. Regarding baseline dengue serostatus, VE against VCD of any serotype was 73.6% (95% CI:57.6%-83.7%) in participants without evidence of prior dengue exposure (n=7,516) and 89.2% (95% CI:77.6%-95.6%) in participants with evidence of prior dengue exposure (n=8,017).

Table 2. Vaccine Efficacy against Symptomatic Virologically Confirmed Dengue through the first 2 years of follow-up (Conditional Exact Method) [10]

Confirmed Dengue	Vaccine			Placebo			Cumulative Vaccine Efficacy (95% CI) %
	Cases	Person-Yrs at Risk	Estimated Incidence (95% CI)	Cases	Person-Yrs at Risk	Estimated Incidence (95% CI)	
	no. (total no.)			no. (total no.)			
Any serotype							
Regardless of serostatus	35/10,215	20,452	0.17 (0.12 to 0.24)	100/5,947	11,927	0.84 (0.68 to 1.02)	79.6 (70.0 to 86.3)
With previous exposure	8/4,994	10,063	0.08 (0.03 to 0.16)	45/3,023	6,092	0.74 (0.54 to 0.99)	89.2 (77.6 to 95.6)
Without previous exposure	26/4,826	9,573	0.27 (0.18 to 0.40)	55/2,690	5,350	1.03 (0.77 to 1.34)	73.6 (57.6 to 83.7)
DENV-1							
Regardless of serostatus	9/10,215	20,463	0.04 (0.02 to 0.08)	50/5,947	11,950	0.42 (0.31 to 0.55)	89.5 (78.7 to 95.0)
With previous exposure	1/4,994	10,065	0.01 (0.00 to 0.06)	19/3,023	6,101	0.31 (0.19 to 0.49)	96.8 (81.0 to 99.8)
Without previous exposure	8/4,826	9,582	0.08 (0.04 to 0.17)	31/2,690	5,365	0.58 (0.39 to 0.82)	85.6 (69.1 to 94.0)
DENV-2							
Regardless of serostatus	26/10,215	20,458	0.13 (0.08 to 0.19)	50/5,947	11,967	0.42 (0.31 to 0.55)	69.6 (50.8 to 81.5)
With previous exposure	7/4,994	10,063	0.07 (0.03 to 0.14)	26/3,023	6,107	0.43 (0.28 to 0.62)	83.7 (63.1 to 93.5)
Without previous exposure	18/4,826	9,579	0.19 (0.11 to 0.30)	24/2,690	5,376	0.45 (0.29 to 0.66)	57.9 (20.8 to 78.1)

* Vaccine efficacy was estimated on the basis of the exact binomial method proposed by Chan and Bohidar,²⁷ and 95% confidence intervals were estimated with the use of Blaker's exact confidence interval.²⁸ The person-years at risk was the cumulative time (in years) until the participant received a diagnosis of the first symptomatic episode of virologically confirmed dengue or until the end of the 2-year follow-up period for each participant, whichever came first. Incidence (per 100 person-years at risk) was calculated as the number of symptomatic, virologically confirmed dengue cases (the number of participants with at least one symptomatic virologically confirmed dengue episode more than 28 days after injection until the end of the follow-up period) divided by the cumulative person-years at risk. Vaccine efficacy according to previous dengue exposure was calculated for participants with dengue serostatus at baseline (those who had preinjection VRNT₆₀ results). Only DENV-1 and DENV-2 were detected during the 2-year follow-up.

Table 3 and Figure 3 summarize three VE calculation methods.

Table 3. Vaccine Efficacy against Symptomatic Virologically Confirmed Dengue through the first 2 years of follow-up (Comparison of VE calculation methods)

Serotype	Serostatus	Method	With follow-up time adjustment	Without follow-up time adjustment
Any Sero-type	Regardless of serostatus	Conditional Exact Method	79.589 (70, 86.26)	79.624 (70.051, 86.284)
		Poisson Regression	79.589 (70.006, 86.111)	79.624 (70.057, 86.134)
		Modified Poisson Regression	79.589 (70.025, 86.102)	79.624 (70.096, 86.115)
	With previous exposure	Conditional Exact Method	89.238 (77.616, 95.576)	89.239 (77.618, 95.577)
		Poisson Regression	89.237 (77.169, 94.926)	89.239 (77.172, 94.927)
		Modified Poisson Regression	89.237 (77.187, 94.922)	89.239 (77.203, 94.92)
	Without previous exposure	Conditional Exact Method	73.581 (57.609, 83.724)	73.65 (57.72, 83.766)
		Poisson Regression	73.579 (57.876, 83.429)	73.65 (57.989, 83.473)
		Modified Poisson Regression	73.579 (57.913, 83.414)	73.65 (58.09, 83.434)
DENV-1	Regardless of serostatus	Conditional Exact Method	89.488 (78.662, 94.959)	89.521 (78.728, 94.975)
		Poisson Regression	89.488 (78.626, 94.83)	89.521 (78.692, 94.846)
		Modified Poisson Regression	89.488 (78.63, 94.829)	89.521 (78.707, 94.843)
	With previous exposure	Conditional Exact Method	96.81 (80.984, 99.844)	96.814 (81.011, 99.845)
		Poisson Regression	96.81 (76.168, 99.573)	96.814 (76.201, 99.573)
		Modified Poisson Regression	96.81 (76.173, 99.573)	96.814 (76.214, 99.573)
	Without previous exposure	Conditional Exact Method	85.551 (69.057, 93.984)	85.616 (69.195, 94.011)
		Poisson Regression	85.551 (68.568, 93.358)	85.616 (68.707, 93.388)
		Modified Poisson Regression	85.551 (68.579, 93.356)	85.616 (68.752, 93.378)
DENV-2	Regardless of serostatus	Conditional Exact Method	69.582 (50.784, 81.48)	69.726 (51.017, 81.567)
		Poisson Regression	69.582 (51.141, 81.062)	69.726 (51.373, 81.153)
		Modified Poisson Regression	69.582 (51.172, 81.05)	69.726 (51.426, 81.132)
	With previous exposure	Conditional Exact Method	83.661 (63.139, 93.523)	83.703 (63.233, 93.539)
		Poisson Regression	83.662 (62.361, 92.909)	83.703 (62.453, 92.926)
		Modified Poisson Regression	83.663 (62.394, 92.902)	83.703 (62.499, 92.917)
	Without previous exposure	Conditional Exact Method	57.904 (20.848, 78.054)	58.195 (21.397, 78.206)
		Poisson Regression	57.903 (22.436, 77.152)	58.195 (22.974, 77.311)
		Modified Poisson Regression	57.903 (22.503, 77.133)	58.195 (23.115, 77.27)

Figure 3. Vaccine Efficacy against Symptomatic Virologically Confirmed Dengue through the first 2 years of follow-up (Comparison of VE calculation methods)

CONCLUSIONS

Three methods of estimating VE, Conditional Exact Method, Poisson regression, and modified Poisson regression, provided consistent VE estimates and CIs for a large clinical trial, with and without follow-up time adjustment.

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